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DETECTION RANGE ANALYSIS IN COGNITIVE RADIO NETWORK OVER FADING CHANNELS

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Abstract:

Objective- In this paper, for cognitive radio networks (CRN) the detection range over different fading channels has been detected which is the key parameter for the better performance of intelligent wireless communication systems. For efficient communication system, the impact of fading medium should be examined on the detection range. Analytical expression for the probability of missed detection and detection range over Rayleigh, Weibull and Laplace fading channels with superimposed lognormal shadowing in cognitive radio network has been derived. Analysis has been done for path loss and detection range to design more effective wireless cognitive radio network.

Design / Methodology/ Approach-The present research paper has analytical approach to reduce fading in cognitive radio network using MATLAB software for different fading channels.

Findings- In this paper detection range has been found to minimize the path loss over increasing distance for wireless cognitive radio network. Investigation of detection range for different fading channels derive new exact and approximated closed-form expressions for average detection probability and average false alarm probability for different fading channels.

Limitations-Present research is based on mathematical calculation for detection range using a defined threshold value; research could have been more authenticated if the threshold value is more accurate for different fading channels and changing rest of the parameters like transmitted power, distance, etc..

Practical implications- This research can help to transmit data from transmitter to receiver having a large

distance between them with minimum path loss and transmitted power.

Originality/Value- The paper includes graphical representation of detection range versus path loss exponent which shows the results of decrease in path loss with increase in distance for different fading channels.

Keywords: Cognitive radio network; detection range. Rayleigh fading; Laplace fading

I. INTRODUCTION

Cognitive radio [6], [7] shows a potential that it is a technology that aims to makes efficient use of the frequency spectrum by means of dynamic spectrum access (DSA). Detecting target in cognitive radio networks is one of the exciting applications. In CRN, the level of connectivity among the mobile devices depends on their spatial diversity, transmission and reception capabilities and characteristics of wireless channel. Detection is of concern for habitat monitoring, security, observation and other defense applications. Cognitive radio networks aims to determine the absence and presence of target of primary user (PU) within the sensing area. Thus, spectrum sensing in the context of cognitive radio system is known to be very challenging task due to hidden PU problem [4] and the fading channels [1]. Therefore, the spectrum sensing is a fundamental function within the cognitive radio network to enable the detection and dynamic sharing of spectrum holes. The problem of detection is treated as a simple hypothesis test in which the null hypothesis H_0 denotes the presence of noise only and the alternate hypothesis

H_1 denotes the presence of primary user. There are two fundamental conditions for CRN, the probability of detection and probability of false alarm. The aim is to keep these two conditions within the predefined threshold. The probability of detection and probability of false alarm are first studied in [5]. Cooperative sensing method is one of the realistic approaches to tackle these conditions. A survey on cooperative sensing can be found in [8]. The impact of Rayleigh fading and impact of interference on wireless network was analyzed in [9], [11]. The analysis of detection range for deterministic channel is presented in [2], but there is a lack of investigation on detection range over different fading channels in cognitive radio network, which is the more practical fading scenario than present one.

In this paper, the analytical expressions for probability of missed detection in cognitive radio network in presence of Rayleigh and Laplace fading channels has been derived. The detection range in different fading channels is also investigated. The simulated results describe the practical scenario for wireless cognitive radio networks.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II briefly describes the system model. In section III, we present the analytical expression for probability of missed detection and detection range over different fading channels. Section IV presents our numerical and simulation results, followed by concluding remarks in section V.

II. SYSTEM MODEL:

Assume that there are N numbers of cognitive radios (CRs) $CR_i \in CR(i = 1, 2, \dots, N)$ and one primary user (PU). The area of sensing has been monitored by CRs continuously, where CR is the set of all cognitive radio nodes. Each cognitive radio node knows their location is also an assumption. The sensing problem of local sensing spectrum is to decide between the following two hypotheses:

$$H_0: y_i(t) = n_i(t), \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N \quad (1)$$

$$H_1: y_i(t) = h_i S_i(t) + n_i(t), \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N \quad (2)$$

Where $y_i(t)$ is the observed signal at the i -th CR, $S_i(t)$ is the signal coming from the primary user, $n_i(t)$ is the additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN), and h_i is the complex channel gain of the sensing channel between the PU and the i -th CR. The noise and the signal are assumed to be unknown, independent and identically distributed (i.i.d). Gaussian random process with zero mean and variance σ_n^2 and σ_s^2 respectively, and

the received signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) is denoted as $\rho = \frac{\sigma_s^2}{\sigma_n^2}$.

III. ANALYSIS OF PROBABILITY OF MISSED DETECTION AND DETECTION RANGE

In this section, derivation of analytical expressions for probability of missed detection and detection range over Rayleigh and Laplace. Analytical results are based on combined path-loss and lognormal shadowing.

A. Rayleigh fading channels:

If the signal amplitude follows a Rayleigh distribution, then the SNR follows an exponential PDF given by [10], [12]

$$f(\rho) = \frac{1}{\bar{\rho}} \exp\left[-\frac{\rho}{\bar{\rho}}\right] \quad \rho \geq 0 \quad (3)$$

Where $\bar{\rho}$ is the average SNR at distance d and can be written as

$$\bar{\rho} = \frac{P_{ts} A d^{-\alpha}}{N_0} \quad (4)$$

The probability of missed detection in this case, P_{mi}^{Ray} , can now be evaluated as

$$\begin{aligned} P_{mi}^{Ray} &= P_r[\rho \leq \lambda] \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{\lambda} \frac{1}{\bar{\rho}} \exp\left[-\frac{\rho}{\bar{\rho}}\right] d\rho \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

After solving (5), value of P_{mi}^{Ray} is

$$P_{mi}^{Ray} = 1 - \exp\left[-\frac{\lambda}{\bar{\rho}}\right] \quad (6)$$

For $P_{mi}^{Ray} \leq P_M^{Max}$ from (6) solution will be

$$1 - \exp\left[-\frac{\lambda}{\bar{\rho}}\right] \leq P_M^{Max} \quad (7)$$

After solving equation (7) we will get

$$\bar{\rho} \leq \frac{\lambda}{\ln\left(\frac{1}{1-P_M^{Max}}\right)} \quad (8)$$

By putting the value of average SNR in (8), we get

$$\frac{P_{ts} A d^{-\alpha}}{N_0} \leq \frac{\lambda}{\ln\left(\frac{1}{1-P_M^{Max}}\right)} \quad (9)$$

After solving (9), the detection range for Rayleigh fading channel is given as

$$d \geq \left[\frac{P_{ts}A}{N_0\lambda} \frac{1}{\ln\left(\frac{1}{1-P_M^{max}}\right)} \right] \quad (10)$$

B. Laplace fading channels:

If the signal amplitude follows a Laplacian distribution, then the SNR follows an exponential PDF given by [3]

$$f(\rho; \mu, \sigma) = \frac{1}{\bar{\rho}} \exp\left(-\frac{|\rho-\mu|}{\sigma}\right) \quad (11)$$

Where $\frac{1}{2\sigma} = \bar{\rho}$

Where $\bar{\rho}$ is the average SNR at distance d and can be written as

$$\bar{\rho} = \frac{P_{ts}Ad^{-\alpha}}{N_0} \quad (12)$$

The probability of missed detection in this case, P_{mi}^{Lap} , can now be evaluated as

$$P_{mi}^{Lap} = P_r(\rho \leq \lambda) = \int_{-\infty}^{\lambda} \frac{1}{\bar{\rho}} \exp\left(-\frac{|\rho-\mu|}{\sigma}\right) \quad (13)$$

After solving (13), value of P_{mi}^{Lap} is

$$P_{mi}^{Lap} = 1 - e\left(-\frac{|\lambda-\mu|}{\bar{\rho}}\right) \quad (14)$$

For $P_{mi}^{Lap} \leq P_M^{Max}$ from (14) solution will be

$$1 - e\left(-\frac{|\lambda-\mu|}{\bar{\rho}}\right) \leq P_M^{max} \quad (15)$$

After solving equation (15) we will get

$$\ln(1 - P_M^{max}) \leq -\frac{|\lambda-\mu|}{\bar{\rho}} \quad (16)$$

By substituting the value of average SNR in (16), we will get

$$\ln(1 - P_M^{max}) \leq -\frac{|\lambda-\mu|}{\frac{P_{ts}Ad^{-\alpha}}{N_0}} \quad (17)$$

After solving (17), the detection range for Laplace fading channel is given as

$$d = \left[\frac{|\lambda-\mu|N_0}{\{\ln(1-P_M^{max})\}P_{ts}A} \right]^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} \quad (18)$$

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

In this section verification of numerical and simulation results for methodical work has been done. The detection range depends on P_M^{max} , α for different cases are discussed here. Mathematical expression in (10) & (18) for detection range are verified by numerical calculation and by simulation using MATLAB software.

In the simulation, the parameters selected are as follows: $A=10\text{dB}$, $P_{ts}=10\text{mW}$, $N_0=0.01\text{mW}$, $\lambda=10\text{dB}$, $K=10\text{dB}$ and varying transmitting power P_{ts} . (31)

Fig.1: Detection range versus path-loss exponent curves for Rayleigh fading channels

Detection range versus path-loss exponent curves for Rayleigh fading channels are shown in Fig.1. From Fig.1, it may be noted that increase in the value of path loss exponent will decrease the detection range. It can also be noted from Fig. 1, that detection range increases

with increase in the value of transmitted power for fixed value of path loss exponent.

In Fig. 2, shows the plot of the detection range versus path-loss exponent curves for Laplace fading channels at $P_{ts}=1, 2, 3, 4\text{mW}$. It can be seen from Fig.2, that detection range increases as the value of path exponent decreases.

Fig.2: detection range versus path-loss exponent curves for Laplace fading channels at different P_{ts}

V. Conclusion:

Detection performance for different fading channels of wireless cognitive radio network has been studied in this paper. Results for the probability of missed detection over different fading channels are derived. The extension of this result is the calculation of detection range over Rayleigh and Laplace. The result simulated describes the practical development for future wireless cognitive radio networks. This work can be unmitigated to the diversity scheme and multiple input multiple output (MIMO) to overcome the multipath fading effect and to augment the performance of wireless network.

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